

**GRADUAL MORPHOLOGICAL DEMARCATION OF SUBSTANTIVE AND
ATTRIBUTIVE MEANINGS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES**

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Аннотация: В работе на примерах градуонимических рядах рассматривается морфологическое разграничение значений предметности и качественности, которые существуют синкретным образом в объективной действительности и дискретизируются (расчленяются) в человеческом мышлении и языке.

Ключевые слова: значение предметности, значение качественности, градуонимический ряд, морфологическое разграничение, градуонимическое микрополе, градуонимическое макрополе.

Objective existence (being) ~ human thinking ~ human language paradigm has a special place in the process of realization of linguistic meanings, in particular, substantive and attributive meanings. If thinking, which actively reflects objective existence, has the capacity for activity such as discretization of syncretic notions and, conversely, syncretization of discrete ones, language, which is the material form of thinking, also has a high activity. It is not a simple shell, box, shaper of thinking, but a unique independent system, a fertile ground for the seeds of thinking – the seeds of thinking are nurtured and grown according to their own rules and produce a rich harvest. The language expresses the substance and attributes separated by thinking and puts them into certain systems, subjecting them to specific laws. For example, when thinking classifies the representatives of substance, objectivity, existence as units of existence derived from signs and attributes such as *apple, dress, human*; and creates concepts like *giant* and *fairy*, language turns them into one of the features of the noun group. It materializes, objectifies the characteristics, like *sweet, high, long, two (dual)* as *redness, sweetness, height, length, duality* and conveys to us unique realities as concepts [3; 4]. The types of attributiveness, distinguished in thinking, such as qualitative and quantitative, stable and variable, similar and different, are formed and grouped in the language as quality and relative adjectives, verb and its participle, adverbial forms, pronouns, adverbs. In addition, specific word-making tools and syntactic tasks are attached to each of them. In this, the unique creative ability of the language is reflected. Language, which is a reflection of thinking, creates **an individual language picture of the world** [1; 2].

Despite the active creativity of language and the fact that it reflects the vision of existence – consciousness (thinking) as a unique system, the real syncretism of substantiveness and attributiveness cannot fail to find its reflection in the language. In the linguistic system, along with the means of showing and expressing the subject matter separately, the attributes are separated into types, along with the means of showing and expressing the substance meanings (SM) and attributive meanings (AM). On the contrary, there are methods and tools that enhance SM and neutralize AM. Separation and description of these is a factor that proves the relevance of the issue before our scientific information – the ability to differentiate, discretize and syncretize SM and AM is manifested in different (gradual) forms in linguistic units [1]. Here, as a scientific concept and

phenomenon, first studied in Uzbek linguistics, and soon became known in world linguistics, graduonymy, deals with general dialectic categories of quantity and quality, as well as the three main law principles – *transition of quantity changes to quality changes and vice versa*, *negation of negation* and *unity and struggle of oppositions* in the language. It should be noted that the phenomenon of linguistic gradation or graduonymy becomes a mechanism for differentiating the meanings of substantiveness and attributiveness. Consequently, the substance and attribute, which are realized in a discrete form of syncrete and mixed beings in the objective existence, are gradually distinguished in human thought and language, in its structural layers, such as phonetic, lexical-semantic, grammatical (layers), and in shallow aspects, namely phrasemic and paremic that are connected with them. It is observed that it demarcates and forms specific *micro-* and *macrofields* in the process of this differentiation. This is clearly visible not only in the system of relative languages, but also in the framework of different system languages, such as Uzbek and English. Below, we will try to justify our opinion on the example of lines reflecting graduonymic relations in distinguishing the meanings of substantiveness and attributiveness in Uzbek and English languages. As mentioned, such tools are divided into three types according to the three levels of language construction and three main signs of the classification of word groups [2]:

1. Lexical-semantic grading in differentiating SM and AM.
2. Morphological grading in differentiating SM and AM.
3. Syntactic gradation in distinguishing SM and AM.

Differentiation of substantive and attributive meanings on the basis of the morphological method, taken as a source of research in this work is related to the division of words into categories and the existence of specific morphological forms for each category. In many cases, these classification forms are combined with semantically corresponding words [5]. For example, the classification of the morphological categorical forms in the language as:

- a) **number** – an objectivity;
- b) **degree** – a static quality;
- c) **ordinal form** – a quantitative sign;
- g) **voice** – a dynamic (convertible) sign

are specialized forms to express their meanings. This can be summarized in the following graduonymic line:

Picture 1

The gradual demarcation line of SM and AM in the Uzbek language

In this case, *number* and *degree*, *ordinal* form, and *voice* in verbs have the characteristic of a mutually gradable microfield in differentiating SM and AM, while the relationship between *number* and *voice* in verbs takes the form of a graduonymic macrofield.

We observe that the morphological order of distinguishing SM and AM in English is somewhat different from that in Uzbek (as mentioned above, it is characterized by the uniqueness of the English grammatical system):

Picture 2

The gradual demarcation line of SM and AM in the English language

In this case, in exchange for the decrease of SM in the line, the increase of AM (and vice versa) occurs at the beginning of the gradation series, where there are articles (A) that have a nominative indicator in English and appear as a strong representative of SM. Different forms of AM – quantitative sign (CN – Category of Number), qualitative sign (CD – Category of Degrees, S – Statives), ordinal form (ON – Ordinal Numerals) and voice form in the verb (CV – Category of Voice) are located between the contrast (opposition) of noun-verb form. It is observed that the gradual morphological pairs, placing nearby, demonstrate microfields of mutual gradations, and accordingly the gradual series **A ~ P/to** reflects the macrofield of the expression of SM and AM. So, in English and Uzbek languages, substantive and attributive meanings are not only expressed in all leading forms and categories in the morphological system, but also in the form of micro- and macro-fields that acquire their own gradual connection.

To sum up, as the substantiveness and attributiveness, which are syncretized in existence, are separated and formed in human thinking and language, the linguistic system does not use the way of completely separating them from each other, but the method of gradation, the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes – morphological means that distinguish the meanings of signs and characteristics are in graduonymic (paradigmatic) relations. The mutual graduonymic relations of the morphological means of demarcation of the meanings of substantiveness and attributiveness in English and Uzbek confirm that such graduonymic series include the stages of **syncretism ~ differentiation ~ opposition**.

In our opinion, many misunderstandings in the language theory is arising as a result of not taking into account the gradual relationship between the logical concepts, especially substantive and

attributive notions in linguistic units. Therefore the study of interlinguistic features can become a solution to some controversial issues not only in private linguistics, but also in general and comparative language studies.

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